

score

D9.12- Newsletters

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V 1.0	Sarah Bonnet (EUR), Maëva Voltz (EUR), Laura De Nale (EUR)	26/06/2025	Final version

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Adaptations
LL	Living Labs

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening *EBA* and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organizations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The purpose of this document is to present an overview of the newsletters published throughout the four-year duration of the SCORE project. These biannual newsletters were designed to provide regular updates on the project's progress, highlight key milestones, and share information about events and activities in which the project consortium participated.

This deliverable aims to illustrate how the newsletters contributed to the project's communication and dissemination strategy, ensuring that stakeholders, partners, and the broader community remained informed and engaged with the SCORE project's developments.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout its four-year duration, the SCORE project committed to producing eight newsletters to communicate key updates, milestones, and results to its community of stakeholders. At the time of submission of this deliverable, seven newsletters have been successfully published

- January and July 2022
- January and July 2023
- January and July 2024
- January 2025

The 8th and last newsletter will be published on 30 June 2025 for the final day of the project. All newsletters are publicly available in a dedicated section of the SCORE website: <https://score-eu-project.eu/newsletter/>.

2. CONTENT

Each SCORE newsletter was designed to keep readers informed about the latest project developments, upcoming activities, and key outputs, while also fostering engagement with the broader community of stakeholders. The newsletters combined updates on project milestones with practical resources and opportunities for involvement.

To maintain consistency and ensure a full coverage of the project's progress, each edition usually featured a selection of regular sections. The main types of content featured in the newsletters were:

- Latest project news and key milestones
- Highlights from the CCLs and their ongoing activities
- Tools and platforms developed within the project
- Publication announcements, such as scientific papers and reports
- Upcoming events and participation in international and European conferences and workshop
- Summaries of past events (e.g., webinars and workshop sessions)
- Clustering activities with other EU projects
- Project videos (e.g., partners interviews) or other communication materials
- Policy recommendations and policy-oriented outputs

This content structure allowed the newsletters to regularly inform stakeholders about the project's progress and related activities.

The following list contains links to all seven of the published newsletters:

- January 2022: [SCORE first newsletter - January 2022 - Score](#)
- July 2022: [SCORE second newsletter - July 2022 - Score](#)
- January 2023: [SCORE third newsletter - January 2023 - Score](#)
- July 2023: [SCORE fourth newsletter - July 2023 - Score](#)

- January 2024: [SCORE fifth newsletter - January 2024 - Score](#)
- July 2024: [SCORE sixth newsletter - July 2024 - Score](#)
- January 2025: [SCORE seventh newsletter - January 2025 - Score](#)

LAUNCH OF THE SCORE PROJECT

July 1, 2021 marked the official start of SCORE, a European research project funded by the European Union's H2020 framework programme aiming to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities.

The project will tackle specific challenges related to sea levels, coastal erosion and extreme weather events using an integrated solution of smart technologies and nature-based solutions.

READ OUR LATEST PUBLISHED DOCUMENTS

- [D1.1 - Literature review report](#)
- [D3.1 Package of procedures for baseline characterization and projections](#)
- [D3.2 Data usage document for the Reference datasets for baseline characterization and projections](#)
- [D5.1 Analysis of the Technical Features of Existing Databases](#)
- [D5.2 Data Management Plan Document, 1st release](#)
- [D9.1 - Plan for exploitation and dissemination of the project results](#)
- [D9.5 - Graphical identity of SCORE](#)

GET INVOLVED!

We are looking for citizens, scientists, policy makers and other stakeholders willing to be **involved** in our activities to address climate change issues relevant to their region.

If you would like to **Join us**, please don't hesitate to contact us!

FOLLOW US ON SOCIAL MEDIA!

The SCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

Copyright © 2022, SCORE, all rights reserved.
This e-mail has been sent to @, [click here](#) to unsubscribe.

Figure 1: Extract from the first SCORE newsletter

3. NEWSLETTER DISSEMINATION AND PROMOTION STRATEGY

To maximise outreach, each newsletter was disseminated through multiple channels, including the SCORE project's official social media accounts (LinkedIn, X/Twitter, Facebook, Instagram), and through targeted email distribution to project partners, stakeholders, and thematic networks active in climate adaptation and coastal resilience.

Thanks to targeted promotion efforts, the SCORE newsletter audience has steadily grown over the course of the project. Promotional campaigns were conducted during events such as international conferences, Living Lab workshops, and webinars, where participants were invited to subscribe either in person or via online sign-up forms. Regular social media posts accompanying each newsletter release also helped to attract new subscribers. As a result of these combined dissemination actions, the SCORE mailing list has reached 595 contacts by June 2025.

Have you received our sixth newsletter?
If not, you can read it here <https://lnkd.in/e5rMcXaG>

You will find out more about:

- Our next events
- Our past webinars
- SCORE's policy briefs and recommendations
- Our free massive open online courses (MOOCs)
- Our tools and platforms
- SCORE's project video
- Our latest news
- SCORE's partners speak out
- Adapt4Coast cluster
- SCORE's participation in Mip4Adapt
- Our latest documents and publications

Do not miss our future newsletters! Subscribe to our mailing list: <https://lnkd.in/dZRTR-wH>

#Newsletter #SCOREproject

Figure 2: Example of social media posts about the newsletter

4. KEY FIGURES AND OUTCOMES

At the time of submission of this deliverable (June 2025), the SCORE project's newsletter activities achieved the following results:

- 7 newsletters published (the final newsletter is scheduled for 30 June 2025, on the last day of the project)
- 595 contacts on the mailing list (at the time of submission of this deliverable) – *see figure below showing the steady increase of recipients*
- Dissemination via social media, partner networks, direct emails, and event promotion
- Newsletters hosted on a [dedicated webpage](#) for easy access and visibility
- The three graphs below display for each newsletter issue, the number of recipients, the opening rate and the click rate. All show very satisfactory result.

This steady, multi-channel dissemination strategy contributed to maintaining engagement within the SCORE community and increasing the visibility of the project's outcomes.

Figure 3: Number of recipients for each newsletter issue

Figure 4: Opening rate per newsletter issue

Figure 5: Click rate per newsletter issue

5.CONCLUSION

The SCORE newsletters played a key role in the project's communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring continuous engagement with the project's community and maintaining visibility for its key activities and outcomes. The consistent growth in subscribers and outreach illustrates the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy and its contribution to the SCORE project's overall impact. The KPI defined for the number of issues published was successfully achieved. While the KPI for the total number of subscribers (target = 1000; results = 595) was not achieved due to a very high target, dedicated efforts were put in place to share the newsletters via other channels (website, social media, emails) and thus ensuring its dissemination outside of the subscribers circle. In addition, each issue performed well in term of opening rate and click rate clearly demonstrating the interest of our subscribers in the newsletter content.

The final newsletter, to be released in 30 June 2025, will provide a comprehensive summary of the project's main outputs and celebrate its achievements.

